

PROMOTING ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS THROUGH CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article emphasizes the importance of integrating environmental education into early childhood learning to nurture a generation of environmentally conscious individuals, discusses the significance of teaching children about nature conservation, instilling a sense of responsibility towards the environment, and fostering a deep connection to the natural world from a young age as well as, highlights the role of parents and educators in cultivating environmental stewardship in children and underlines the positive impact of early environmental education on shaping future attitudes and behaviors. By exploring practical methods and engaging children in activities that promote environmental awareness and sustainability, the article advocates for building a sustainable and eco-friendly future through the proactive involvement of children in caring for our planet.

Key words: environment, natural resources, animal and plant world, perfect person, compassion for nature, global problem, ecology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ekologik ta'limni boshlang'ich davrdagi ta'limga integratsiyalashgan holda atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilishda ongli avlodni tarbiyalash muhimligi, bolalarni tabiatni asrashni o'rgatish, atrof-muhitga nisbatan mas'uliyat hissini uyg'otish va chuqur bog'lanishni rivojlantirish muhimligi muhokama qilinadi. Yoshlikdan tabiat olami, shuningdek, bolalarda atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilishni rivojlantirishda ot-onalar va o'qituvchilarning rolini va erta ekologik ta'limning kelajakdagi munosabat va xatti-harakatlarni shakllantirishga ijobiy ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada, shuningdek, amaliy usullarni o'rganish va bolalarni ekologik xabardorlik, barqarorlikni targ'ib qiluvchi faoliyatga jalb qilish, sayyoramizga g'amxo'rlik qilishda faol jalb qilish orqali barqaror va ekologik toza kelajakni qurish tarafdori bo'lishga chorlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: atrof-muhit, tabiiy resurslar, hayvonot va o'simlik dunyosi, komil inson, tabiatga mehr-oqibat, global muammo, ekologiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждается важность воспитания сознательного поколения в вопросах охраны окружающей среды путем

интеграции экологического образования в начальное образование, обучения детей охране природы, привития чувства ответственности за окружающую среду и глубокой связи с важностью развития. Мир природы с раннего возраста также подчеркивает роль родителей и педагогов в развитии природоохранной деятельности у детей и положительное влияние раннего экологического воспитания на формирование будущих взглядов и поведения. Статья также призывает детей стать сторонниками построения устойчивого и экологически чистого будущего, изучая практические методы и вовлекая детей в деятельность, способствующую экологическому осознанию, устойчивости и активному участию в заботе о нашей планете.

Ключевые слова: окружающая среда, природные ресурсы, фауна и флора, совершенный человек, доброта к природе, глобальная проблема, экология.

Currently, processes of renewal and modernization are taking place in all corners of our country, as in other countries. From this we can understand that renewal began with creation. Most of the innovations being created now are smart technologies and electronics. Of course, new innovations surprise each of us, make another task easier and save us time. However, just as everything has its pros, it also has its cons. We decided to promote the idea of informing about such harmful aspects, their harmful vices that threaten the life of living and inanimate nature. After all, only young people with this kind of knowledge are likely to be the foundation that will put an end to the problems that are becoming a global problem.

Today, all laws and regulations that are being reformed in all educational centers of our country are aimed at developing the younger generation into mature and comprehensively developed people. Therefore, one of the main goals of the reforms carried out in our republic is to promote the ideas of awakening in young people historical and cultural values, customs, and a sense of love for the country where they grow up.

Starting from an early age, teaching children about the principles of protecting the environment and making them aware that they are a part of Mother Nature by observing and implementing actions to improve the surrounding environment is one of the effective ways. Children in grades 1-4 certainly benefit from simple observations and games, expressing their results through drawing in visual arts classes or preparing things from paper. As they grow older, they independently observe and analyze all changes. For the

development of children along this path, parents also play a significant role. Children go through many adventures from the beginning of school age, they can already understand the environment that surrounds them by the time they reach school. However, they themselves often do not know how to explain in what manner to teach and how to demonstrate their attitudes toward it. Therefore, starting from that time, parents should provide their children with sufficient information about animals and plants, know their task to feed or entertain them. In addition to this, in practice, through their own attitudes towards nature, it is possible to provide lessons, as a positive result of their encouraging the child begins the adaptation process, and they begin to look at the environment with a beautiful eye, start to love nature from the bottom of their heart, and continue to do so. Therefore, it is important for parents to play a very important role in a child's psychological and physical development, they form the main foundation for choosing the right path in the future.

Now we all can understand that the geographical and political location and structure of the world is changing every day. At the same time as several other such problems are being dealt with, several problems related to the formation of children's understanding of nature are being identified in all strata of the world's population. Today, it is very sad that a large part of our society is indifferent to our environment. Arousing the feeling of love for mother nature in the hearts of young people remains one of the only tasks of the current situation. The reason for this is that when humans abuse the environment and all the living and non-living things it encompasses, nature retaliates in kind to those who put it in this situation. One of the reasons for global problems increasing day by day is that electronics have spread to human life everywhere like a virus and become famous. Everyone from seven to seventy years old uses social networks. As a result, due to the use of social networks by everyone, absolute and unique changes in the surrounding environment become apparent. Therefore, due to the different perceptions of parents and children, through the inability of parents to tell their children differently from their parents because of disagreements, children only realize causing harm to ecology, as a result, all countries worldwide suffer. The only way to find a solution is to start taking positive actions by carefully observing the surrounding environment, understanding to what extent it has reached a critical state, and starting to take positive actions against it, while slightly restricting from using social networks, parents appreciate the seriousness of the situation and the degree to which it has deteriorated and take positive actions against it. For example, by joining a

simple volunteer group to clean up the streets or planting young seedlings with the aim of extending the 'green belt' and participating in ecological improvement through raising them, it is possible to contribute to the improvement of our ecology. Therefore, if we have a strong desire from our side to carry out that work in a kind and sincere way, that alone is enough. Additionally, if healthy thoughts about our ecology are formed in the minds of every teenager, our society will begin to rise to higher heights. It is advisable to organize various question-and-answer games in nature and spend high-quality time, and organize activities about making a home for helpless animals and birds left on the street and not harming them. After practicing these methods, children can begin to think about nature and begin to learn how they should act in a good relationship with nature. Paying attention to a new problem will have a high probability of starting to improve the problems of watering such problems. Due to the fact that there is a need to settle on the form of general attention, to strengthen its high value, to develop an effective communication network, to search for high-level ways of speaking about global problems. This atmosphere will be related to keeping the youth, nature gifted joints straight. They get to learn new knowledge, and in the process of improvement, by developing their cultural skills, they begin to learn in the same environment and overcome the past that leads to its transfer to the younger generation. Because paying attention to nature leads to defeating its high value, allowing the workers to update their methods and raising questions about the appreciation of the nature of our country. In order to carry out such reforms, it will be necessary to develop special methods for children and apply them in practice. The purpose of this is the process of introducing young children to the world around us, making a worthy contribution to their development as a perfect person in the future. Inculcating such ideas in their minds will not only help them to be educated, but also to make them aware of the proper use of natural resources, the safety of endangered animals, how important trees are to our ecology, and many other similar issues. including positive change such as having prevention skills and changing our world for the better. We can give several examples of the idea of using the above-mentioned special methodology:

- Bringing children to the bosom of living nature and providing necessary and interesting information about the world of animals and plants;
- Caring for pets, their useful aspects for our lives, parents telling children about them;

- To show how important natural resources are for our country's finances and our daily needs, and what problems we will face if they run out;
- Showing interesting videos about the proliferation of cars and the harm caused by the smoke and oil produced by various factories and factories to our biosphere and the underwater world;
- Showing scenes and slides about not throwing waste in the right place, how such inappropriate actions can harm their lives;
- Organizing various question-and-answer games in nature and spending more quality time;
- It would be appropriate to use such methods as teaching skills about how to make a home for helpless animals and birds left on the street and how to avoid harming them.

During the period of their development, by instilling the values of compassion to nature from a young age, we should shape children to show love towards nature, to understand the important role they play in ecological development, and if anyone does any wrongdoing towards nature, what consequences this may bring, and animals and plants are also lively beings similar to humans, we need to instill only compassion in the minds of children. Albert Schweitzer says, "When we take a deeper look at nature, we understand that it is full of life, it is the essence of life itself, and we realize that we are merging with every life present in nature". Thus, realizing that it is the work of a foolish and brainless person to cause harm to a part of ourselves, and strengthening our resolve to stay far away on the path of these actions. Therefore, we have no right to destroy what nature has created.

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